

The Usage Of Electronic Information Resources By Amman Arab University Undergraduates Of English Language And Translation

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Abstract

Usage of electronic information resources is a vital element in the current distance education. This study was carried out to identify the advantages and the ease of use of the electronic information resources offered by Amman Arab University Library. The study also investigated students' satisfaction and highlighted the challenges faced by English language and translation students when using these resources. This was a mixed-methods study that applied a questionnaire followed by qualitative interviews. The participants were 150 female and male students from the Department of English Language and Translation. The findings revealed that electronic information resources were highly helpful and flexible to use. The students were satisfied with the electronic information resources. In contrast, some students reported that they faced several challenges such as internet issues, lack of skills and lack of orientation programs. Conclusion and recommendations regarding the use of these resources were provided.

Introduction

The technological revolution has been granting a significant role to electronic information resources in the educational process as these resources provide the students with most recent information. These resources consist of various forms such as periodicals, databases and e-books. These resources have been integrated in the most libraries which have witnessed important developments in their missions in the process of academic achievement and scientific research. University students use these resources in searching and preparing their academic work as they offer electronic content and advance tools that make it easy to find the best information from its sources and present it to students on the electronic devices with one click. Amman Arab University is a leading university that bestows the students with various electronic resources as well as traditional ones. The students have access to different international databases like EBSCO and ProQuest which offer thousands of e-books, journals, newspaper, etc.

Today, e-learning, considering the Corona pandemic, became a top priority for all educational institutions. (Bataineh & et al. 2021) The transition from traditional education to e-learning education has been boosting the important role of these resources. Students are more aware about the benefits of these resources. Yet, it is well known that these resources are not sufficiently used by the students. This study is carried out to examine the level of English language and translation students' utilization of the electronic information resources offered at Amman Arab University in Jordan. The study also investigated their attitudes toward utilizing these electronic information resources to develop their academic skills, and the challenges faced by the students when using these resources. The research aims at identifying a) the advantages, b) the ease of use, c) the students' satisfaction of the electronic information resources and d) highlighting the challenges faced by English language and translation students when using English language and electronic information resources. The research attempts to answer the following study questions:

1. What are the advantages of using the electronic information resources by English language and translation students?
2. Are the electronic information resources easy to use?
3. Are the students satisfied with the electronic information resources?
4. What are the challenges faced by English language and translation students when using electronic information resources?

The study was limited to students of English language and translation department at Amman Arab University in the first semester of the academic year 2020/2021.

Literature View and Past Studies Electronic Information Resources

An electronic resource is termed as a resource that necessitates internet access, electronic device, and data in electronic form. According to Tsakonas (2006) electronic information resources include resources available on the internet such as e-journals, e-books, online database, web sites, CD-ROM, Diskettes, and other portable computer databases. To cope with the recent transferring from conventional education to distance education and to meet students' needs and satisfactions, university libraries are fully keen on dealing with electronic information resources and making them available for their students and researchers. As Aljaraideh & Al Bataineh (2019) emphasize that information and communication technology play a significant role in the teaching and learning process, Shuling (2007) also asserts that electronic information has grown into a key resource in the academic institutions. Ellis & Oldman (2005) state that dealing with electronic information resources, students have the chance to access to global information resources. As a result of the recent transition from traditional education to e-learning education, using these resources become a key part in the academic institutions.

Amman Arab University Library

As the study investigated the level of English language and translation students' utilization of the electronic information resources offered at Amman Arab University, it is important to shed the light on AAU library. It was established in 1999 with numerous sources of information to serve the teaching and learning processes at the university as well as scientific research process. The library has witnessed a speedy development in its collections and a remarkable enhancement in the provided services. The library offers university students with special and latest sources of information including books, dictionaries, encyclopedias, scientific papers, periodicals, scientific theses and dissertations, and databases. Furthermore, the library is equipped with modern computers and internet connection. The library has subscribed to different international databases like EBSCO and ProQuest which offer thousands of e-books, journals, newspaper, etc.

Past Studies

As the use of electronic resources is still a point of discussion for many scholars, they have studied the advantages and disadvantages of these resources and how the students use these resources. (Akuffo & Budu 2019, Dattatraya & et al. 2013, Mehla 2018, Sharma. 2019, Singh 2013, Toyo 2017, Tlakula & Fombad 2017).

Tlakula & Fombad (2017) investigated the undergraduate students' level of use and awareness of the electronic resources. The results showed that undergraduate students, at the university of Venda in South Africa, use these resources in elementary and limited. The level of awareness of these resources is low. It also showed that the level of awareness and training in the use of these resources is basic.

A study conducted by Akuffo & Budu (2019) examined thirty-three postgraduate students' level of awareness of e-resources, how they access and use e-resources, the reasons of utilizing e-resources and the advantages of and difficulties in utilizing e-resources. The study showed high awareness levels, adequate computer skills, numerous advantages, utilization of e-resources for academic uses and insufficient search skills of most students due to lack of training. Access, search and retrieve, and staff-related difficulties were the main constrictions to use e-resources.

In Nigeria, Toyo (2017) studied the undergraduates' use of electronic resources and their information literacy skills. The study revealed that they use numerous e-resources and have the needed skills to cope with electronic resources. It was also found that these resources are advantageous for the students' academic performance. Yet, student encountered several barriers such as lack of awareness of these resources, academic workload, slow internet access, ineffectual communication channels and erratic power supply.

Since this study deals with using electronic resources, it is also important to shed the light on using of these resources by faculty members in the academic institutions. Dattatraya & et al. (2013) were mainly concerned with the usage of electronic information resources and some related issues. The results of the research revealed that the users used e-resources to the maximum due to awareness of e-resources. Besides, Singh (2013) found that all the subjects were positively using e-resources, namely, online databases and e-journals while few of them were using e-books. Another study tackled by Sharma (2019) examined the awareness, accessibility, and use of information and communication technologies. The findings of the study showed that more than 3/5th of the research scholars visit Vivekananda library to read books, with a majority of being aware of the library facilities and the availability of e-resources. 39.55% of the users were aware of library orientation program conducted in the library. In addition, Mehla (2018) found that 70% of male and 30% of female respondents, who are between 25–30 years, used electronic resources. Yet, the participants reported slow access speed and non-availability of needed e-resources were the serious obstacles.

This study was carried out to elucidate the use of electronic resources by undergraduate students in Jordan. In the Jordanian context, the use of electronic resources by the undergraduate students have not yet been fully elucidated. Tawalbeh & et al. (2015) investigated electronic resources and services in a public university library and examined problems and obstacles faced by the students. The researchers noted that they effectively utilize databases in their educational process, though one of the main obstacles is shortage of computer labs. In another study conducted by Hamsfri (2019), Jordanian students utilize these resources in moderate level for academic purposes. It was also found that lack of training and orientation are the main obstacles faced by the students. In their study (2019), Humaidat & Yasin explored the use of electronic information resources by English language department staff at the University of Jordan. The results of the study showed that they were satisfied with the electronic services provided by their institution. Furthermore, the study concluded that the majority of the users were encountering the problem of being unable to access some electronic sources until they order a prepaid subscription.

Methodology

Research Design

This research is a mixed-methods study that applied an electronic questionnaire followed by distance qualitative interviews. Questionnaire was used to gather the data to identify the advantages, the ease of use and the students' satisfaction of the electronic information resources. Qualitative interview was adapted to pinpoint the challenges faced by English language and translation students when using electronic information resources.

Research Participants

The participants of the research consist of 107 students female and male from the department of English language and translation in the first semester of the academic year 2020/2021. The participants represent different ages from 18 to 45 years old form different study levels as shown in the followings graphs:

Figure 1. Research Participants

Instrumentations

To conduct the current study, questionnaire and interview were used.

The researchers prepared a questionnaire that included four parts. The first portion included questions related to age and study level. The second part was related to usefulness of the electronic recourses. The third part aimed at investigating the ease of use of electronic recourses. The fourth part was to reveal the level of students' satisfaction of electronic recourses. Students answered 23 questions by checking one answer from the following 5 choices: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree.

For the validity of the questionnaire, a jury of university professors were asked to judge the questionnaire questions. Their comments and recommendations were taken into consideration and the questionnaire was amended accordingly. Besides, to check the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot study was applied to 15 students out of the research participants in two different sittings in two weeks time. The questionnaire questions were constant.

To grant triangulation for the data, Twenty-five Students were then interviewed to identify their challenges when using English language and electronic information resources. Extensive interviews with selected students are very much required seeing that some individual information such as feelings and attitudes are not measurable through mere texts. Shaari & Bataineh (2015)

Finding and Discussion

To answer the first question, "what are the advantages of using the electronic information resources by English language and translation students?" The students answered seven questionnaire items of the advantages of these resources.

Table 1. The Advantages of the Electronic Information Resources

Item	S-A	A	N	D	S-D
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1	I find that electronic information resources are highly effective.	27.1%	42.1%	23.4%	6.5%	9%
2	I believe that electronic information resources increase my scientific productivity.	29%	39.3%	23.4%	8.4%	0.0%
3	Electronic information resources motivate me to control my academic activities.	20.6%	38.3%	30.8%	8.4%	1.9%
4	Electronic resources of information help me accomplish my academic duties.	27.1%	44.9%	20.6%	6.5%	9%
5	Electronic information resources save time.	35.5%	40.2%	14%	7.5%	2.8%
6	Electronic information resources meet my scientific needs.	27.1%	32.7%	33.6%	5.6%	9%
7	By using electronic information resources, I get all the results I expect.	15%	31.8%	38.3%	11.2%	3.7%

Regarding the above table, the majority (69.1%) of the students found that electronic information resources are highly effective while (31.7%) of the students don't believe that electronic information resources increase [their] scientific productivity. Students are aware that electronic information resources assist positively in scientific productivity specially pursuing their academic duties as (72%) of them agreed that "Electronic resources of information help [them] accomplish my academic duties." This result concurs with common knowledge that technology and internet have positive effects on human scientific productivity as resources are shared more easily.

Also, data showed that (75.7%) of the participants supported the statement that "Electronic information resources save time." Around half of the students indicated that "Electronic information resources meet [their] scientific needs," as only (14.9%) of them disbelieved that "By using electronic information resources, I get all the results I expect." It is known that these resources grant students a quick access into a diversity of information resources. This helps them to meet their scientific needs. Thus, these resources are advantageous for the students. This finding concurs with many researches such as those by Akuffo & Budu, S. (2019), Toyo (2017), Tawalbeh & et al. (2015), Humaidat & Yasin (2019) and Dattatraya & et al. (2013) who stressed the advantages of these resources. Yet, the findings disagree with Hamsfri (2019) who noted that Jordanian students use these resources in moderate level due to different reasons such as lack of training and orientation. To answer the second question, "are the electronic information resources easy to use?" The students answered seven questionnaire items of the ease of use of these resources.

Table 2. The Ease of Use of these Resources

	Item	S-A	A	N	D	S-D
1	I find it easy to use electronic information resources.	24.3%	48.6%	21.5%	4.7%	9%
2	I believe that electronic information resources are flexible to use.	27.1%	48.6%	21.5%	5.6%	2.8%
3	Electronic information resources require little effort.	25.2%	43.9%	21.5%	5.6%	3.7%
4	I can use electronic information resources without instructions.	16.8%	42.1%	26.2%	13.1%	1.9%
5	I found consistency in the components of electronic information resources.	13.1%	43.9%	38.3%	4.7%	0.0%
6	I can easily undo any errors in electronic information resources.	11.2%	29%	27.1%	29%	3.7%
7	I am able to use electronic information resources successfully.	14%	54.2%	27.1%	4.7%	0.0%

As shown in table 2, only (13.7%) of the students found it difficult to use electronic information resources while the majority of the students believed that electronic information resources are flexible to use, require little effort, and they can use electronic information resources without instructions. Besides, (57%) of the students agrees that "I found consistency in the components of electronic information resources" while (32.7%) of them disagreed that "I can easily undo any errors in electronic information resources". In general, it was obvious that the students were able to use electronic information resources successfully as only (4.7%) of them disagreed that "I am able to use electronic information resources successfully." These results are inconsistent with Tlakula & Fombad (2017), who found that undergraduate students use these resources in elementary and limited level and Hamsfri (2019), who found that Jordanian students use these resources in moderate level.

Generally, the students hold positive beliefs about electronic resources and found these resources easy to use. The results are in line with the fact that young people are more likely to use technology as they were born into the digital era. The results are consistent with many studies such as Akuffo & Budu (2019), Toyo (2017) and Tawalbeh & et al. (2015).

To answer the third question, "are the students satisfied with the electronic information resources?" The students answered seven questionnaire items of the student's satisfaction of these resources.

Table 3. The Student's Satisfaction of these Resources

	Item	S-A	A	N	D	S-D
1	I am very satisfied with the results of electronic information resources.	16.8%	40.2%	28%	11.2%	3.7%
2	I recommend using electronic information resources to friends.	15%	48.6%	26.2%	9.3%	0.9%
3	Using electronic information resources is fun.	15.9%	43%	23.4%	12.1%	5.6%
4	I see electronic information resources perform as they are supposed to.	13.1%	48.6%	29%	7.5%	1.9%
5	I feel that I need electronic information resources constantly.	21.5%	34.6%	35.5%	8.4%	0.0%

As revealed from the results, it is obvious that students were satisfied with the electronic information resources. Thus, they recommended these electronic information resources to friends. The above data shows that (57%) of the students were very satisfied with the results of electronic information resources and (58.9%) of them believed that using electronic information resources is fun. The data also indicates that the majority of the students agreed that the electronic information resources perform as they are supposed to and they needed electronic information resources constantly. The results reflect the positive beliefs that students hold about these resources as they were satisfied with these resources. The results agree with Humaidat & Yasin (2019), Dattatraya & et al. (2013) and Singh. (2013) who revealed that the users positively used these e-resources.

To answer the fourth question, "what are the challenges faced by English language and translation students when using electronic information resources?" The students were interviewed to report about their challenges they faced during their using the electronic information resources.

According to the students' answers, the challenges were as follows:

1. **Internet speed and availability.** Most of the interviewed students affirmed that they faced difficulty with internet speed, network coverage and lack of internet bundles that hindered them from accessing these resources during the distance education. This is due to the pandemic and unexpected turning into distance education.
2. **Lack of specialized resources:** Most of the students reported that there are not enough resources in the field of English Language and Translation. AAU library has subscribed to only two databases, EBSCO and ProQuest, and it found that students were not satisfied with the number of the databases available in the AAU library.
3. **Lack of skills and orientation programs.** The majority of the students reported that they did not have any training or induction about using these resources. They were not satisfied with search option and selecting the right keyword to reach the information they need.
4. **Lack of awareness and knowledge:** Some students reported that they are not aware of the existence of such resources.

The above-mentioned obstacles reveal the reality of the challenges encountered by Amman Arab University students. These results consent with Akuffo & Budu (2019), Bernard et al. (2004) and Toyo, O. D. (2017).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The main purpose of this study was to examine the use of electronic information resources and the challenges faced by English language and translation students at Amman Arab University. The study findings show that electronic information resources are highly helpful in increasing students' scientific productivity, maintaining the academic activities and duties, saving students' time, and meeting the students' scientific needs. This reflects the positive attitude toward the use of electronic information resources. The findings also reveal that most of the students have no difficulty using these resources as they believe that these resources are flexible to use and consistent in the components. Thus, they are able to use electronic information resources successfully. It is obvious that the ease of use of these resources is confirmed by the majority of the students. Besides, it is evident that students of this study were satisfied with the electronic information resources. Thus, they recommended these electronic information resources to friends. Despite what was said above, some students reports that they face some challenges such as internet speed and availability, lack of specialized resources, and lack of skills and orientation programs.

To increase the student knowledge about the importance of the electronic resources, orientation programs should be held by a specialized library employee at the beginning of every academic year where the students are introduced to these resources and other services provided by the library. A library staff should be delegated for each of the university's faculties, who coordinates with the lecturers in the faculties and his task is to determine the prescribed titles and provide support for the educational and research process.

For successful learning process and effective use of the electronic information resources, the university should link these resources that have been subscribed or purchased, directly to the university's e-learning platform and the library's website. More specialised databases should be available for the students such as The Handbook of Translation Studies, Translation Studies Bibliography & Translation Studies Abstracts, Linguistics and Language Behavior Abstracts (LLBA), Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, MLA International Bibliography.

Generally, the findings of the current study deliver helpful insights into the use of electronic information resources by Amman Arab University students of English language and Translation. Amman Arab University should take these findings into consideration in designing effective e-learning programs that meet the students' needs. The results can also help lecturers of English language and translation to develop better language learning and teaching processes.

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